

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF DASHMULYADI KWATHA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TAMAKA SHWASA W.S.R. BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

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ABSTRACT

Prevalence of respiratory disorders is rapidly increasing owing to industrialization and globalization. Pollution, impaired immunity, stress along with faulty diet and life style is mostly responsible for aggravating non communicable disease like Bronchial Asthma which is a more prevalent disorder in developed countries and in urban areas. It is a global burden and requires early measures for its prevention and treatment so that complications associated with this disease can be prevented at the earliest. Its signs and symptoms closely resemble with *Tamaka Shwasa* in *Ayurveda* which is mainly a *vata kaphaj* disease and having *Pitta* as its origin site. According to *ayurvedic* principles those drugs having *vata kapha nashak*, *ushna* property and *vatanulomana* in nature are required for the management of *Tamaka Shwasa*. Many drugs mentioned in *ayurvedic* classics are having above properties and most of

them are having '*Dashmoola*' as ingredient owing to its properties like *Shothanashak*, *Deepana-pachana* and *Vatanulomana*. Few of these have been tried satisfactorily in controlled & planned clinical studies. On the basis of these studies and the principles opined

by *Ayurvedic Acharyas*, a systematic review study has been undertaken regarding the role of *Dashmulyadi Kwatha* in the management of *Tamaka Shwasa*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, Bronchial Asthma, *Tamaka Shwasa*, *Dashmulyadi Kwatha*.

1. INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, *Tamaka Shwasa* has been mentioned as a '*swatantra vyadhi*' having its own etiology, pathology and management and also a subtype of disease *Shwasa* where impairment in the free flow of *prana vayu* due to *vaikrat kapha* produced as a result of *agnimandya* and *sama rasa* results in the *viloma gati* of *vata* and manifests in the form of mainly *shwasakricchata, kasa, pinasa etc.* Disease *Tamaka Shwasa* is mainly having *kapha, vata* predominance and its site of origin is *pitta*. It is a *yapya vyadhi* involving *pranavaha, udakavha* and *annavaha srotas*. Its treatment principle mainly involves use of *kaphavatahara, ushna* and *vatanulomana* drugs and dietary regime. On the basis of clinical presentation, *Tamaka Shwasa* can be put in parlance with disease Bronchial Asthma of modern science. Bronchial asthma is a global health burden mainly found in developed countries and in urban areas owing to growing industrialization, poor diet and lifestyle, reduced immunity and is mainly characterized by a disease of tracheobronchial tree where repetitive episodes of breathlessness, chest tightness, cough etc. are present on exposure to inducing and trigger factors. In Modern science its management mainly involves use of bronchodilators and preventer drugs which on the other hand is associated with increased drug dose dependency on long term usage.

Lots of research work has already been done on *Tamaka Shwasa* where use of *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa* has not only proven cure for the disease but also reduces the drug dose dependency significantly. According to *Ayurveda*, any drug available in the whole world can be used as medicine to achieve the desired objective by *yukti*.^[1] So, for the present systematic review study, *Dashmulyadi Kwatha* has been choose owing to its *tridosha shamaka, aama pachana, vatanulomana, deepana pachan, ushna virya, vedanasthapana, shothahara, shwasa-kasahara, balya, brihana, rasayana, raktashodhaka* properties.

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

To review the role of *Dashmulyadi Kwatha* in the management of *Tamaka Shwasa* w.s.r. Bronchial Asthma.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Review of different Ayurvedic classical texts, modern texts and journals.

4. Disease Review

4.1. Ayurvedic Review

In *Ayurvedic* classics, *Tamaka Shwasa* is mentioned as subtype of disease *Shwasa*. *Shwasa roga* are five in number, out of them *Kshudra Shwasa* is present as symptom in most of the diseases & it does not require any medication and is curable, whereas *Maha Shwasa*, *Urdhva Shwasa* & *Chinna Shwasa* are present at the terminal stages of various diseases and are incurable in nature. *Tamaka Shwasa* is a '*SwatantraVyadhi*' *Yapya* in nature & having its own etiology, pathology & management.

4.1.1 Nidana

Tamaka Shwasa is a disease where multi factorial causation is responsible for its development. Its *nidana* is mainly of two types: *Bahya* (Extrinsic) – like *raja*, *dhuma*, *vata* etc. and *Abhyantar* (Intrinsic) – *kapha* & *vata dosha* vitiation. It can also occur as *Nidana-arthkara roga* or as secondary manifestation of other diseases like *Kasa*, *Atisara*, *Jwara* & *Pandu*.

Tamaka Shwasa is an episodic disease. So, role of *Vyanjaka Hetu* in this disease is more. *Vyanjaka Hetu* is stimulating, precipitating or aggravating factors. These also cause aggravation of the symptoms in an existing disease or precipitation of the *Samprapti* of the disease. The knowledge of these *Hetus* is useful in preventing the aggravation of disease.

Main Aharaj and *viharaj nidana (vata prakopaka)* related to *Tamaka Shwasa* are: *Rukshanna* (Fat free diet), *Vishamashana* (Irregular diet), *Adhyashana* (Frequent meals), *Anashana* (Fast), *Sheetashana* (intake of cold food), *Vishasevana* (Toxins), *Sheetambu* (Cold water), *Vishtambhi bhोजना* (slowly digested food).^[2] and *Rajas* (Dust), *Dhuma* (Smoke), *Vata* (Wind), *Sheetsthana-sevan* (toreside at cold places), *Sheetambu* (cold water), *Ativyayama* (over exercise), *Gramyadharm* (over indulgence in sex), *Ati-Aptarpana* (over malnutrition), *Marmaghata* (Trauma over vital organs), *Vega vidharana* (suppression of urges), *Suddhyatiyoga* (excessive purification), *Kantha pratigraha* (throat trauma), *Urah Pratigraha* (chest trauma), *Karmahata* (exhausted), *Adhwahata* (excessive work).^[3]

Main Aharaj and viharaj nidana (kapha prakopaka) related to Tamaka Shwasa are *masha* (Black gram), *nishpava* (Beans), *pinyaka* (Tila paste), *pishtanna* (paste-preparations), *jalaja mansa* (flesh of Aquatic animals), *guru bhojan* (Heavy diet), *amakashira* (Unboiled milk), *dadhi* (Curd), *anupa mansa*, *tila taila*, *abhishyandi ahara*, *shleshmala dravya*, *shaluka* (Lotus rhizome) and *abhishyandi upacharas*.^[4]

Main Aharaj nidana (Pitta prakopaka) related to Tamaka Shwasa are *Vidahi*^{[5],[6]}, *katu*, *ushna*, *lavana*^[7], *amla*, *lavana*.^[8]

Vyanjaka hetu in *Tamaka Shwasa* are *Megha* (cloud), *Ambu* (water), *Sheeta* (cold), *Sleshmavardhaka* things (*kapha* increasing items).^[9]

Nidanarthkara roga for *Tamaka Shwasa*: *Apatarpana* (Under nutrition), *Anaha* (Mal digestion), *Vibandha* (constipation), *Dhatukshaya* (Emaciation), *Atisara* (Diarrhoea), *Daurbalya* (Weakness), *Urahkshata* (Trauma in chest), *Pandu roga* (Anaemia), *Udavarta* (reverse motion of natural urges), *Alasaka* (food materials remain undigested), *Visuchika* (acute gastroenteritis), *Visha sevana*, *Raktapitta*, *Jwara* (fever), *Kasa*, *Amapradosha* (Mal digestion), *Pratikshaya* (Coryza), *Chardi* (Vomiting).^[10]

The etiological factors either in the form of the faulty dietetic habits, behavioral errors, or due to the abuse by the environmental factors causing morbidity of *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha*, or upsetting the functioning of *pranavaha srotas* leads to the establishment of the lingering disease *Tamaka Shwasa*. Due to the detrimental effects of *nidana* there occurs accumulation of the *Kapha Dosha* in the *pranavaha srotas*, which in turn obstructs the free channel of the *Pranavayu* leading to *Prana vilomata* and that is how the attack of *Tamaka Shwasa* begins.

4.1.2 Samprapti

In *Charaka Samhita* the *samprapti* of *Tamaka Shwasa* has been explained under three occasions. Common *samprapti* of *Hikka* and *Shwasa* i.e., The morbid *Vata* which is obstructed by *Kapha* makes the vitiation of *Prana*, *Udaka* and *Annavaaha srotas*, and finally lodges in the chest region causing *Shwasa* and *Hikka disorder*,^[11] specific *samprapti* of *Shwasa* i.e., when the *Kapha* along with *Vata* obstructs the *srotas*, the hindered *vayu* trying to overcome the obstacle moves in all directions results in *Shwasa*^[12] and specific *samprapti* of *Tamaka Shwasa* i.e., when the flow of *prana vayu* is reversed due to obstruction of *srotas* (channels) by *kapha*, it gets vitiated & surrounds the neck & head leads to excess secretion of

dushta kapha which leads to *pinasa* & *ghurghurukam* sound is produced. This condition leads to acute onset of dyspnoea which suffocates the *prana*. He has a feeling of entering into darkness, thirst develops & faints, becomes unconscious. Paroxysmal attack of *kasa* occur. Unable to expectorate, he feels irritation & once the expectoration of *dushta kapha* occurs, gets relief for moment. Hoarseness of the throat develops & there is difficulty in speaking. Patient suddenly wakes up with a sense of suffocation. Dyspnoea increases & he has to sit on the bed. So, he feels comfortable while sitting & desires for hot things. His eye is raised upward; there is profused perspiration on forehead & remains in state of distress. His mouth dries & suffers from paroxysmal attack of dyspnoea. This condition is exacerbated due to clouds, rain, cold winds & air coming directly. The other psychosomatic factors like *chinta*, *shoka*, *bhaya* also aggravate the *Shwasa roga*. This condition is known as *Tamaka Shwasa*. It is *yapya* disease (i.e. it can be only managed), if it is of recent origin then totally curable.^[13]

Samprapti ghatak

Main *Dosha* involved is *Kapha* & *Vata* (dominances); *kapha* (*avlabhaka* & *kledaka*); *vata* (*prana*, *udana*, *samana*), *Dushya*: *Rasa dhatu*, *Srotas*: *Pranavaha srotas*; *Udakavaha srotas*; *Annavaaha Srotas*, *Udbhava sthana*: *Pitta sthana*, *Adhithana*: *Uraha*, *Phuppusa* (*kapha sthana*), *Sroto dushti lakshana*: *Sanga*, *Vimarga gamana*, *Atipravritti*, *Ama*: *Ras gata* (*Agni mandya janya Ama*), *Agni*: *Jathargni* (*Vishama*), *Vyadhi*: *Amashayotha*, *Swabhava*: *Ashukari* & *Chirkari*, *Vyadhi marga*: *Abhyantra Marga*.

4.1.3. Purvarupa (Prodromal symptoms)

No specific *Purvarupa* has been explained for *Tamaka Shwasa* but the *Purvarupa* explained in the context of *Shwasa* holds good for *Tamaka Shwasa* also. Main *purvarupa* of *shwasa* according to acharya Charaka are *Anaha*, *Parshvashula*, *Hritapida*, *Prana vilomata*,^[14] *Bhakta dwesha*, *Arati*, *Vaktra vairasya*, *Aruchi*,^[15] *Shankh nistod*.^[16]

4.1.4. Rupa (Symptoms)

Following tables lists the *Rupa* of *Tamaka Shwasa* as mentioned by different *Acharyas*.

Sl. No.	Rupa	Ch. ^[17]	Su. ^[18]	A.H. ^[19]	M.Ni. ^[20]
1	<i>Aruchi</i>	-	+	-	-
2	<i>Asino labhate saukhyam</i>	+	-	+	+
3	<i>Bhrashamartimana</i>	+	-	+	+
4	<i>Jvara</i>	+	+	-	+
5	<i>Ghurghurukam</i>	+	+	+	+
6	<i>Kanthodhwanasa</i>	+	-	-	+
7	<i>Kasa</i>	+	+	+	+

8	<i>Kricchena bhashitum</i>	+	-	-	+
9	<i>Maghachhenne shawasavridhi</i>	+	+	+	+
10	<i>Muhursh wasomuhush chaivavadhamyate</i>	+	+	+	+
11	<i>Na chapi labhate nidra</i>	+	-	-	+
12	<i>Nishcheshtata</i>	+	-	-	+
13	<i>Parshva shula</i>	+	-	+	+
14	<i>Pinasa</i>	+	-	+	+
15	<i>Pramoha</i>	+	+	+	+
16	<i>Pranapeedakam teevra shwasa</i>	+	-	+	+
17	<i>Shleshmnaye amuchyamane tu bhranshambhavati dukhitah</i>	+	-	-	+
18	<i>Swedyata lalaten</i>	+	+	+	+
19	<i>Sheetopcahrena prashmana(Santamaka)</i>	+	-	-	+
20	<i>Tamasa varddhyati(Pratamaka)</i>	+	-	-	+
21	<i>Tamah pravesha</i>	+	+	+	+
22	<i>Trishna</i>	-	+	+	-
23	<i>Uchhuh netra</i>	+	-	+	+
24	<i>Ushnena chaiv abhinanditi</i>	+	-	+	+
25	<i>Vamathu</i>	-	+	-	-
26	<i>Vepathu</i>	-	+	-	-
27	<i>Vishushkyasyata</i>	+	-	+	+

4.1.5. Types of Tamaka Shwasa^[21]

Maharshi Charaka has mentioned two-allied stages of *Tamaka Shwasa* known as two types or further complication of disease proper i.e. *Pratamaka* and *Santamaka*. *Sushruta* and *Vagbhata* have only mentioned the name as *Pratamaka*, which includes clinical manifestation of *Santamaka*.

Pratamaka shwasa: Patients suffering from *Tamaka Shwasa* when gets afflicted with fever and fainting, the condition is called as *Pratamaka Shwasa*. It is suggestive of involvement of *Pitta dosha* in *Pratamaka Shwasa*. It is aggravated by *Udavarta*, dust, indigestion, humidity (*Kleda*), suppression of natural urges, *Tamoguna*, darkness and gets alleviated instantaneously by cooling regimens.^[22]

Sanatamaka shwasa: When the patients of *Pratamaka Shwasa* feels submerged in darkness, the condition is called as *Santamaka Shwasa*.^[23] Though *Chakrapani* has mentioned these two as synonyms of each other *Charaka* refers them as two different ailments representing two different stages of *Tamaka Shwasa*, these two conditions differ from each other according to intensity of attack. This can be taken as the severe stage of *Pratamaka*.

4.1.6. *Upashya and Anupshaya*^[24]

In *Tamaka Shwasa*, *Upashaya* and *Anupashaya* have been explained while mentioning the *lakshanas* of the disease these are as follows

Upashaya in Tamaka Shwasa: *Ushna Ahara Vihara, Asino Labhate Saukhyam* (feels comfortable to breath in sitting position), *Shleshma Vimokshante Sukham* (slight relief in breathlessness on spitting out the sputum), Factors, that reduces the *Kapha* vitiation brings out relief.

Anupashaya in Tamaka Shwasa: *Sheeta Ahara Vihara, Sheeta Ambu* (cold water), *Shayanasya Shvasa Piditaha* (discomfort worsens on lying), *Meghabhi Abhivardhate* (cloudy weather worsens the attack), *Pragvata* (breeze), *Sleshmala* (*Kapha* aggravating factors add to the disease).

4.1.6. *Sadhya – Asadhyata (Prognosis)*

According to *Acharya Charaka*, *Hikka* and *Shwasa* appearing as a complication of other diseases have worst prognosis.^[25] *Tamaka Shwasa* in general is described as *yapya* (palliable) disease. However, in individual with recent origin of disease, person of *pravara bala* or both said to be *Sadhya*.^[26] *Sushruta* opined *kasa, shwasa & vilambika* are very difficult to cure like setting in together of fire, wind & thunder.^[27] Regarding *Tamaka Shwasa* he says that it is a disease which can be cured with much difficulty. If it appears in debilitated individuals its prognosis becomes very difficult.^[28]

4.1.7. *Chikitsa*

Nidana Parivarjanam: Prime importance in *Shwasa Chikitsa* is the avoidance of causative factors.^[29] -Different treatment modalities have been explained in ayurvedic texts regarding the management of disease *Tamaka Shwasa*. In *Vegavastha*, *Acharyas* have emphasized on the *Shodhana* therapy in the starting of *Chikitsa* may be an emergency treatment after that *Shamana yoga* are described and Chronic management of the *Avegavastha*, where the frequency, duration and intensity of the attacks are minimized / totally cured to give a quality life to the patient. The choice of management of *Shwasa*, *Alpabala* patient is *Tarpana* and *Shamana*. *Shodhana* therapy (*Vamana* and *Virechana Karma*) should be administered only if extremely essential, if the patient is having good *Dehabala* and *Satwabala*, and when all other measures fail.

According to Acharya Charak, *Shamana Chikitsa* drugs must possess the qualities of *Vatakaphaghna*, *Ushna* and *Vatanulomana*.^[30] Also, acharya has emphasized about the fact that, any remedy which aggravates *vata* and pacifies *kapha* or which pacifies *vata* and aggravates *kapha* or which pacifies both *vatakapha* or which pacifies only *vata* should be used for the management of *Tamaka Shwasa*.^[31]

4.2. MODERN REVIEW

4.2.1. Definition: Global initiative for Asthma defines asthma as a heterogenous disease characterized by chronic airway inflammation with a history of respiratory symptoms such as wheeze, shortness of breath, chest tightness, and cough that vary over time and in intensity, together with variable expiratory airflow limitation.^[32]

4.2.2. Prevalence: It is more prevalent in developed countries than developing ones, more in children (15%) than adults (10%), more in urban than rural areas. Nearly, 8% to 10% of total population suffers from it. In India, the prevalence of Asthma has been found to be around 7% in the majority of surveys done. However, it has been reported to vary from 2% to 17% in different study populations, the disease can start at any age, but in majority it starts before 10 years of age. It is twice as common among boys than girls, whereas in adults the male to female ratio is usually equal.^[33]

4.2.3. Aetiological factors: of asthma are divided into two groups: inducing factors and trigger factors. Inducing factors induce asthma in susceptible persons and these include genetic factors, obesity, viral infections in early life and exposure to tobacco smoke. Trigger factors such as allergens, vigorous exercise, viral infections, drugs, food, psychological factors, occupation, gastro-oesophageal reflux etc. can provoke symptoms in subjects already having asthma. Some factors such as viral infection and occupational sensitizers act as both inducer and trigger factors.^[34]

4.2.4. Pathophysiology of Bronchial Asthma: Asthma is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by airway narrowing as a result of increased airway secretions, smooth muscle contraction, and airway wall thickening. Secretion of proinflammatory cytokines and inflammatory cell infiltration plays a major role in the pathogenesis of asthma. Episodic breathlessness, wheezing, cough and chest tightness are important symptoms of bronchial asthma. These symptoms show a characteristic pattern of diurnal variability of worsening during night and early morning. It may lead to disrupted sleep due to cough and wheeze.

There is an increased mucus production which is thick, mucoid and difficult to expectorate. History of recurrent episodes of asthma caused by one or more trigger factors is important for the diagnosis of bronchial asthma. However, between episodes, patients usually remain symptom free.^[35]

4.2.5. Classification of Bronchial Asthma^[36]

The most widely accepted classification of asthma severity was that recommended by the National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute's (NHLBI) National Asthma Education and Prevention Program (NAEPP) Expert Panel Report 2. These guidelines placed major emphasis on diagnosis (including classification of asthma) and management, which included a stepped approach to asthma treatment. The NAEPP classification relies on an assessment of asthma symptoms and lung function at the time the patient is being evaluated and prior to commencement of treatment. Three variables are considered in classifying asthma severity, namely, daytime symptoms, nighttime symptoms, and lung function. Abnormalities within each of these three variables are graded into four separate categories of severity. Overall asthma severity is categorized according to the worst individual variable.

NAEPP classification of Asthma severity

Symptoms severity	Days with symptoms	Night with symptoms	PEFR FEV1	PEF Variability
Step 4 Severe Persistent	Continual	Frequent	< 60 %	> 30 %
Step 3 Moderate Persistent	Daily	> 1 / week	> 60 % - < 80 %	< 30 %
Step 2 Mild persistent	> 2 / week, but <1/ day	> 2 / month	> 80 %	20-30 %
Step 1 Mild Intermittent	< 2 / week	< 2 / month	> 80 %	< 20 %

4.2.6. Diagnosis: For diagnosis of Bronchial Asthma, Blood examination (increased eosinophil count, raised IgE), Sputum examination, Histamine challenge test for airway hyperresponsiveness, chest radiograph, CT of chest, Identification of trigger factors, Skin prick test, measurement of lung function by Peak flowmeter and Spirometer, Lung volumes and diffusing capacity, Oximetry and arterial blood gas analysis,^[37] can be carried out.

4.2.6. Management of Asthma: Patient education (identify and reduce exposure to risk factors, assess monitor and treat asthma, manage exacerbation), drug therapy with bronchodilators or relievers like Beta-2-agonists, anticholinergics, methylxanthines) and controllers or preventers like inhaled corticosteroids, systemic corticosteroids, anti-leukotrienes and mast cell stabilisers, anti- IgE antibody, antigen specific immunotherapy.^[38]

5. Drug Review

For the present study *Dashmulyadi Kwatha*^[39] has been chosen from *ayurvedic* literature of *Bhaishajya Ratnawali*.

Pharmacological properties and contents of *Dashmulyadi Kwatha*^[40] can be tabulated as

Sl. no.	Drug	Botanical name / Family	Rasa Panchak	Doshaghata	Part Used / Part
1.	<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos / Rutaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Madhura Guna-Laghu Virya-Sheeta Vipaka-Madhura Karma-Mutrala</i>	<i>Tridoshaghna</i>	Root/ 1
2.	<i>Agnimantha</i>	<i>Premna mucronate / Verbenaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Guna-Laghu, Ruksha Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Shyavathuhara</i>	<i>Vatahara, Kaphahara</i>	Root/ 1
3.	<i>Gambhari</i>	<i>Gmelina arborea / Verbenaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Tikta, Kashaya Guna-Guru Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Dipana, Pachana, Bhedana, Medhya, sothahara, Vishaghna</i>	<i>Tridoshajit</i>	Root/1
4.	<i>Shyonaka</i>	<i>Oroxylum indicum / Bignoniaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Kashaya, Tikta Guna-Laghu, Ruksha Virya-Sheeta Vipaka-Katu Karma- Dipana, Grahi</i>	<i>Kaphapitta shamaka</i>	Root/1
5.	<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum suaveolens / Bignoniaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Kashaya, Tikta Guna-Laghu, Ruksha Virya-Anushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Ruchya</i>	<i>Tridoshahara</i>	Root /1
6.	<i>Shalparni</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum / Fabaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Tikta, Madhura Guna- Guru, Snigdha Virya- Ushna Vipaka- Madhura Karma-Balya, Mutrala, Brihmana, Rasayana, Vrishya</i>	<i>Tridoshahara, Vatahara</i>	Root/1
7.	<i>Prishniparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta / Fabaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Madhura, Katu, Amla, Tikta Guna- Laghu, Sara Virya- Ushna Vipaka- Madhura Karma- Vrishya, Dipana, Samgrahi, Sothahara, Sandhaniye,</i>	<i>Tridoshahara, Vatahara</i>	Root/1

			<i>Angamardprashamana, Jivanu nashak, Bala vardhaka</i>		
8.	<i>Gokshura</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris / Zygophyllaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Madhura, Tikta Guna-Guru, Snigdha Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Madhura Karma-Balya, Brimhana, Dipana, Keshya, Mutrala, Shothahara, Vrishya, Vedanasthapana</i>	<i>Kaphahara</i>	Whole plant/1
9.	<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Solanum surattense / Solanaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Katu, Tikta Guna-Laghu, Ruksha Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Dipana, Pachana, Amadoshanashak, Kanthya, Shothahara</i>	<i>Kapha vata hara</i>	Whole plant/1
10.	<i>Brihati</i>	<i>Solanum indicum / Solanaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Tikta, Katu Guna- Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna Virya- Ushna Vipaka- Katu Karma- Dipana, Grahi, Hridya, Keshya, Pachana, Vedanasthapana</i>	<i>Kaphahara,, Vatahara</i>	Whole plant/1
11.	<i>Shati</i>	<i>Hedychium spicaticum / Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Guna-Laghu, Tikshna Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Mukha- shoshana, Grahi, Shoolahara</i>	<i>Kaphavataghna</i>	Rhizomes/1
12.	<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata / Asteraceae</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta Guna- Guru Virya- Ushna Vipaka- Katu Karma- Amapachana</i>	<i>Kapha vatahara</i>	Leaf/1
13.	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum / Piperaceae</i>	<i>Rasa- Katu, Tikta, Madhura Guna- Snigdha, Laghu Virya- Anushna Vipaka- Madhura Karma- Dipana, Ruchya, Rasayana, Hridya, Vrishya, Vatanulomana</i>	<i>Vatahara, Kaphahara,</i>	Fruit/1
14.	<i>Shunthi</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale / Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Rasa- Katu Guna-Laghu, snigdha Virya-Ushna Vipaka- Madhura Karma-Dipana, Pachana, Anulomana, Aamdoshahara,</i>	<i>Vatakaphapaha</i>	Rhizome/2

			<i>Hridya</i>		
15.	<i>Pushkarmula</i>	<i>Inula racemosa / Asteraceae</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta, Katu Guna- Laghu Virya- Ushna Vipaka- Katu Karma- Kaphavatajit</i>	Kaphavatajit	Root/1
16.	<i>Karkatshringi</i>	<i>Pistacia integerrima / Anacardiaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Kashaya, Tikta Guna-Guru Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Kasahara, Urdhvavatajit, Hikkanigrahana</i>	<i>Kaphavatahara</i>	Gall/1
17.	<i>Tamalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus niruri / Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Kashaya, Tikta, Madhura Guna- Laghu, Ruksha Virya- Sheeta Vipaka- Madhura Karma- Rochana, Dahanashni,</i>	<i>Pittashamaka</i>	Root, stem and leaf/1
18.	<i>Bharangi</i>	<i>Clerodendrum serratum/ Verbenaceae</i>	<i>Rasa- Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Guna-Laghu, Ruksha Virya-Ushna Vipaka- Katu Karma-Dipana, Pachana, Shwasahara, Ruchya</i>	<i>Vatahara, Kaphahara</i>	Root /1
19.	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia/ Menispermaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Tikta, Kashaya Guna-Laghu Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Madhura Karma-Samgrahi, Balya, Dipana, Rasayana, Raktashodhaka</i>	<i>Tridoshashamaka</i>	Stem/1
20.	<i>Chitrakmoola</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica/ Plumbaginaceae</i>	<i>Rasa-Katu Guna-Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna Virya-Ushna Vipaka-Katu Karma-Dipana, Pachana, Grahi, Arshohara, Shulahara</i>	<i>Kaphavatahara</i>	Root/1

Probable mode of action of *Dashmulyadi Kwatha* in the management of *Tamaka Shwasa*

Dashmulyadi Kwatha consists of many ingredients which are excellently balancing each other in terms of *Rasa-pachaka*, *vata kaphahara*, *deepana*, *pachana*, *balya*, *brihan*, *shothahara*, *bhedan* and *vatanulomana* properties which are required to break the pathogenesis of the disease *Tamaka Shwasa*.

Vata kaphahara property of most of the contents like *Agnimantha*, *Kantkari*, *Brihati*, *Shati*, *Rasna*, *Pippali*, *Shunthi*, *Pushkarmula*, *Karkatshringi*, *Bharangi*, *Chitrakmoola* alleviates both *vata* and *kapha*, which are the main doshas in the pathogenesis of *Tamaka Shwasa*. The main factor in this disease as in many other diseases is *Ama* and the *Deepana* properties of the drugs like *Gambhari*, *Shyonaka*, *Prishniparni*, *Gokshura*, *Pippali*, *Guduchi* along with *Deepana -pachana* properties of the drugs like *Gambhari*, *Kantkari*, *Brihati*, *Shunthi* and *Chitrakmoola*. *Aamdoshnashaka* properties of *Kantkari*, *Rasna* and *Shunthi* will help in the digestion of *Ama* by kindling the *Jatharagni* as well as *Rasagni* and *Bhutagni*. Further *Shothahara* karma of most of the contents like *Gambhari*, *Agnimantha*, *Prishniparni*, *Gokshura* and *Kantkari* will neutralize the *srotorodha* in *Pranavaha srotas* created by *Sama Vata* facilitating the free flow of *Prana vayu*. *Vatanulomana* property of ingredients like *Shunthi* and *Pippali* maintains the normal flow of *vata*. *Balya* properties of *Shalparni*, *Prishniparni* and *Guduchi*, *Balya* and *Brihana* properties of *Shalparni* and *Gokshura*, *Rasayana* properties of *Pippali*, *Guduchi* will further prevent the *prakopa* of *vata* due to *dhatu kshaya* and *Vedanasthapana* and *shoolahara* properties of *Gokshura*, *Brihati*, *Shati* and *Chitrakmoola* will help in easing out the symptoms like *parshvashoola* / *urah shoola* associated with *Tamaka Shwasa*.

The pharmacological studies already reported on the individual drugs also favour its effect in disease Bronchial Asthma which can be summarized as.

Sl. no.	Drug / Botanical name / Family	Pharmacological action
1.	<i>Bilva</i> / <i>Aegle marmelos</i> / <i>Rutaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, free radical scavenging activity, spasmogenic, digestive, carminative. ^[41]
2.	<i>Agnimanth</i> / <i>Premna mucronateel</i> / <i>Verbenaceae</i>	anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant. ^[42]
3.	<i>Gambhari</i> / <i>Gmelina arborea</i> / <i>Verbenaceae</i>	Anti-helminthic, Anti-inflammatory. ^[43]
4.	<i>Shyonaka</i> / <i>Oroxylum indicum</i> / <i>Bignoniaceae</i>	Anti-stress, Purgative, Anti-spasmodic, Anti-inflammatory. ^[44]
5.	<i>Patala</i> / <i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i> / <i>Bignoniaceae</i>	Anti-viral, expectorant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-ulcer properties. ^[45]
6.	<i>Shalparni</i> / <i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> / <i>Fabaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, analgesic, and antimicrobial. ^[46]
7.	<i>Prishniparni</i> / <i>Uraria picta</i> / <i>Fabaceae</i>	anti-oxidant, cardioprotective, anti-hypertrophic, anti-ulcer, hepatoprotective, anti-amnesic, wound healing and, anti-inflammatory activities. ^[47]
8.	<i>Gokshura</i> / <i>Tribulus</i>	Antiuro lithiatic, Antimicrobial, Antihelminthic, Cardiotonic,

	<i>terrestris / Zygophyllaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Hypolipidemic, Immunomodulatory, Antispasmodic, Analgesic, Aphrodisiac, Antidiabetic, Anti-tumour, Hepato-protective, Anti-cancerous, Anti-oxidant, CNS modulator properties. ^[48]
9.	<i>Kantakari / Solanum surattense / Solanaceae</i>	Potent bronchodilator, anti-asthmatic, and expectorant. ^[49]
10.	<i>Brihati / Solanum indicum / Solanaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and analgesic actions. ^[50]
11.	<i>Shati/ Hedychium spicaticum/ Zingiberaceae</i>	Anti-allergic, Anti-spasmodic, Bronchodilator, anti-inflammatory, anti-tussive, Expectorant. ^[51]
12.	<i>Rasna / Pluchea lanceolata / Asteraceae</i>	Anti-oxidant. ^[52]
13.	<i>Pippali / Piper longum / Piperaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, anti-asthmatic, anti-depressant, anti-bacterial, analgesic, anti-oxidative and immunomodulator activity. ^[53]
14.	<i>Shunthi / Zingiber officinale/ Zingiberaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, hypolipidemic and anti-viral activity. ^[54]
15.	<i>Pushkarmula / Inula racemosa / Asteraceae</i>	Bacteriostatic, Fungistatic, Anti-inflammatory, Bronchodilator. ^[55]
16.	<i>Karkatshringi / Pistacia integerrima / Anacardiaceaea</i>	Expectorant, Anti-spasmodic, Anti-inflammatory and Anti-allergic. ^[56]
17.	<i>Tamalaki / Phyllanthus niruri / Euphorbiaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, anti-asthmatic, anti-microbial, immunomodulator, anti-viral, anti-oxidant. ^[57]
18.	<i>Bharangi / Clerodendrum serratum / Verbenaceae</i>	Anti-inflammatory, antiallergic, expectorant, bronchodilator, anti-asthmatic, and antimicrobial activities. ^[58]
19.	<i>Guduchi / Tinospora cordifolia / Menispermaceae</i>	Immunomodulator, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, immunomodulatory, antioxidant. ^[59]
20.	<i>Chitrakmoola / Plumbago zeylanica / Plumbaginaceae</i>	antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antimicrobial properties ^[60] , Analgesic. ^[61]

6. DISCUSSION

Respiratory disorders are increasing today at a fast pace due to number of causes like air pollution, faulty dietary habits, low immunity, stress etc. Asthma is a chronic inflammatory airway disease that typically manifests itself as chest tightness, wheezing, cough, and dyspnea, all symptoms that are associated with airways obstruction. They can occur spontaneously often during the night or the early morning hours, following exercise, or after exposure to an allergen. These symptom and airflow limitation are associated with an exacerbation of the underlying airway inflammation. The cells and mediators involved in these exacerbations are probably different depending on the stimulus (ex: nocturnal, exercise induced, allergen induced, or +6virus induced); however, the end results probably include

smooth muscle contraction and inflammation that resolve spontaneously or with appropriate therapy.^[62]

Management of Bronchial Asthma mainly involves patient education regarding the avoidance of allergens and other precipitating factors, drug therapy with bronchodilators or relievers like Beta-2-agonists (ex: Epinephrine), anticholinergics (ex: Ipratropium), methylxanthines (ex: Aminophylline) and controllers or preventers like inhaled corticosteroids, systemic corticosteroids (anti-inflammatory drugs), anti-leukotrienes (ex: Montelukast) and mast cell stabilisers (Cromolyn Sodium), Anti-IgE antibody (ex: Omalizumab), antigen specific immunotherapy. The complications of Asthma exacerbations are pneumothorax, lung atelectasis, pneumonia, and asthmatic status. Persistent Asthma can also develop into fibrosing bronchitis, small bronchi deformation and obliteration, emphysema and chronic respiratory failure as complication. In case of early detection and adequate treatment the prognosis for the disease is favorable. Treatment becomes serious in severe persistent and poorly controlled asthma.

On the basis of etiological factors and clinical presentation of the disease Bronchial Asthma can be put in parlance with *Tamaka shwasa*, which is a independent disease having its own etiology, pathogenesis and treatment. *Tamaka Shwasa* is considered as a *vata kaphaj vikara* of *pranavaha srotas*, having *pitta* as its main site of origin. Its attack mainly precipitates at night and during its attack patient feels as if entering into the darkness. Its main causative factors are mainly *Bahya hetu* like *Dhuma* (Smoke), *Raja* (dust) etc. and *abhyantara hetu* i.e., *vata* and *kapha prakopaka* factors like *Ativyayama* (excessive exercise), *Sheetasthanavasa* (residing in cold areas), *Guru bhojan* (heavy diet) and *sheetbhojana* (cold articles) etc along with *vyanjaka hetu* i.e., precipitating or aggravating factors. These factors are responsible for vitiation of *vata* which in turn vitiates *kapha* and causes *mandagni* and facilitates the formation of *Sama rasa* which on the other hand is responsible for the formation of *sama kapha as its mala*. This *mala rupa kapha* is mainly involved for encouraging the *srotavarodha* in the form of *kaphavritta vata* in *Pranavaha srotas* where free flow of *Prana vayu* is hampered and the attack of disease is precipitated. Its main clinical features are *shwasakrichhata*, *kasa*, *pinasa*, *parshvashula* etc. Its prognosis is good if diseases is of recent origin or in patients with *pravara bala*, otherwise it is a *yapya* (palliable) disease. This disease is very difficult to cure if not treated in the early stages or if get chronic or is found as

complication of other diseases. Ancient Acharyas has clearly indicated the use of *Ushna*, *Vatakapha nashak* and *vatanulomana* drugs and regime for the management of the disease.

Keeping in view the pathogenesis, clinical manifestation and severity of the disease drug having the property of *Deepana- pachana*, *Ushna virya*, *Vatakapha nashak*, *aamdoshanashak*, *Vatanulomana*, *Shothahara*, *Kasashwasa hara*, *balya*, *brihana*, *rasayana* is required so that the free flow of *prana vayu* is attained, and *vitiating* of *prakupita vata* is prevented, so that the attack of *Tamaka shwasa* is relieved.

Contents of *Dashmulyadi Kwatha* are having the properties which are required to break the pathogenesis of *Tamaka Shwasa* and can be summarized as.

S.No	Action required from drugs for <i>Samprapti vighatana</i> of <i>Tamaka Shwasa</i> and management of <i>Tamaka Shwasa</i>	Contents of <i>Dashmulyadi Kwatha</i> participating in <i>Samprapti vighatana</i> and managements of <i>Tamaka Shwasa</i>
1.	<i>Vata-kaphaghnam</i>	<i>Agnimantha</i> , <i>Kantkari</i> , <i>Brihati</i> , <i>Shati</i> , <i>Rasna</i> , <i>Pippali</i> , <i>Shunthi</i> , <i>Pushkarmula</i> , <i>Shunthi</i> , <i>Pushkarmula</i> , <i>Karkatshringi</i> , <i>Bharangi</i> , <i>Chitrakmoola</i> , <i>Bharangi</i> , <i>Chitrakmoola</i> .
2.	<i>Kapha hara</i>	<i>Gokshura</i>
3.	<i>Tridoshahara</i> , <i>Vatahara</i>	<i>Shalparni</i> , <i>Prishniparni</i> ,
4.	<i>Tridoshahara</i>	<i>Bilva</i> , <i>Gambhari</i> , <i>Patala</i> , <i>Guduchi</i> , <i>Shalparni</i> , <i>Prishniparni</i> ,
5.	<i>Pitta shamaka</i>	<i>Tamalaki</i>
6.	<i>Ushna Virya</i>	<i>Agnimantha</i> , <i>Gambhari</i> , <i>Shalparni</i> , <i>Prishniparni</i> , <i>Gokshura</i> , <i>Kantakari</i> , <i>Brihati</i> , <i>Shati</i> , <i>Rasna</i> , <i>Shunthi</i> , <i>Pushkarmula</i> , <i>Karkatshringi</i> , <i>Bharangi</i> , <i>Guduchi</i> and <i>Chitrakmoola</i> .
7.	<i>Deepana</i>	<i>Gambhari</i> , <i>Shyonaka</i> , <i>Prishniparni</i> , <i>Gokshura</i> , <i>Pippali</i> , <i>Guduchi</i>
8.	<i>Deepana pachana</i>	<i>Gambhari</i> , <i>Kantakari</i> , <i>Brihati</i> , <i>Shunthi</i> , <i>Chitrakmoola</i> .
9.	<i>Aamdosha nashak</i>	<i>Kantakari</i> , <i>Rasna</i> , <i>Shunthi</i> .
10.	<i>Vatanulomanam</i>	<i>Shunthi</i>
11.	<i>Shothahara</i>	<i>Gambhari</i> , <i>Agnimantha</i> , <i>Prishniparni</i> , <i>Gokshura</i> , <i>Kantakari</i> .
12.	<i>Kasa hara</i> , <i>Urdhva vatajit</i>	<i>Karkatshringi</i>
13.	<i>Shwasahara</i>	<i>Shati</i> , <i>Pushkarmoola</i> , <i>Tamalaki</i> , <i>Bhrangi</i>
14.	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Pippali</i> , <i>Guduchi</i> , <i>Shalaparni</i>
15.	<i>Balya</i>	<i>Shalaparni</i> , <i>Prishniparni</i> , <i>Guduchi</i>
16.	<i>Brihana</i>	<i>Shalaparni</i> , <i>Gokshura</i>
17.	<i>Vedanasthapana/ Shoolahara</i>	<i>Gokshura</i> , <i>Brihati</i> , <i>Shati</i> , <i>Chitrakmoola</i>
18.	<i>Raktashodhaka</i>	<i>Guduchi</i>

The effect of this polyherbal drug combination is to liquefy the thick bronchial secretion and help in cough expectoration. Most of the drugs are having *Tikta*, *Katu rasa* and *Ushna virya* which is responsible for alleviation of *vata* and *kapha* dosha. Most of the drugs are having anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, immunomodulator, bronchodilator, anti-microbial, anti-allergic properties thereby may decrease the inflammation of tracheobronchial tree and may provide strength to respiratory system and may further prevent the attack of Bronchial asthma.

7. CONCLUSION

Ayurveda always prioritize preventive and promotive aspect related to health as compared to the curative aspect for any disease. Here also, *Dashmulyadi kwatha* may act as preventer drug for enhancing the periods between two attacks by providing strength to the respiratory system, by increasing the immunity of the body, reducing the inflammation or may act as a controller drug for providing the relief during the attack of *Tamaka Shwasa* owing to its properties like *Deepana-pachana*, *Aamdoshnashaka*, *shothahara*, *Kasa-shwasahara*, *balya*, *brihana*, *rasyana*, *Vedanasthapana* and *raktashodhana*.

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